

Studies in Alkaloids*

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Today, I should like to speak at some length on two alkaloids, carpaine and echitamine, to whose structure-elucidation, my collaborators and I have contributed in some measure. These two alkaloids belong to entirely different structural types, but the investigations have this in common, many unexpected twists and turns and many unexpected developments.

The alkaloid carpaine was isolated in 1890 by Greshoff, but it was only in 1965, that a total structure for this alkaloid could be written. The first important structural investigations were carried out by Barger and Robinson in the 1930's. It was established that carpaine contained a large-membered lactone ring¹, that it had a straight chain of at least seven methylene groups, since azelaic acid was the largest fragment produced on oxidation. Selenium-dehydrogenation yielded carpyrine and apocarpyrine, which gave reactions typical of pyrroles. Carpaine and some of its derivatives were found to contain a C methyl group. On these grounds carpaine was assigned structure (I)². The problem was taken

up for reinvestigation by Rapoport and coworkers³ and at the Presidency College, Madras, in the early 1950's. Rapoport and coworkers obtained the following results.

Carpaine was submitted to two Hofmann degradations, with hydrogenation at each stage to yield myristic acid $C_{14}H_{28}O_2$. The carbon chain of carpaine should therefore have a straight chain of fourteen carbon atoms and the Barger-Robinson formula became untenable. Palladium-charcoal dehydrogenation of carpaine yielded deoxycarpyrinic acid

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1. G. Barger, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 466.

2. G. Barger, R. Robinson and T. S. Work, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 711.

3. H. Rapoport and H. D. Baldrige, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 343; *ibid.*, 1952, 74, 5365; H. Rapoport, H. D. Baldrige and E. J. Volcheck, *ibid.*, 1953, 75, 5290; H. Rapoport and E. J. Volcheck, *ibid.*, 1956, 78, 2451.

which was shown to be 8-[2'-(6'-methylpyridyl)] octanoic acid (II). A piperidine rather than a pyrrolidine ring was present in carpaine.

Methyl carpamate was submitted to two Hofmann degradations, followed by reduction at each stage. The nitrogen-free material on oxidation yielded dodecandioic acid (III) and 12 keto tetradecanoic acid (IV).

III

IV

On the basis of this evidence carpaine was assigned structure (V)

Independent evidence leading to the same structure was provided by the work at Presidency College. Dehydrogenation of ethyl carpamate using Pd/C yielded, ethyl carpyrinate⁴ (VI) whose structure was proved by a synthesis⁵ (Chart I).

Chart I

4. T. R. Govindachari and N. S. Narasimhan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 2635.

5. T. R. Govindachari, N. S. Narasimhan and S. Rajadurai, *ibid.*, 1957, 560.

Carpaine was also degraded to 5-methoxy-2-octylpyridine by the sequence of reactions shown⁶ (Chart II).

Chart II

These experiments furnished independent proof for the Rapoport structure.

Evidence about the stereochemistry of carpaine was also obtained⁷. Ethyl(-) deoxycarpamate was prepared as shown (Chart III).

Chart III

HCl, m.p. 130-131°, $[\alpha]_D = -10.3^\circ$

6. T. R. Govindachari, N. S. Narasimham and S. Rajadurai, *ibid.*, 1957, 558.

7. T. R. Govindachari and N. S. Narasimham, *ibid.*, 1955, 1563.

Catalytic reduction of deoxycarpyrinic acid in acid solution gave racemic *cis*-deoxycarpamic acid. It is known that reduction in acid solution of 2,6-dialkyl pyridines leads exclusively to the *cis*-isomer. Reduction of deoxycarpyrinic acid with sodium and alcohol yielded two racemates. One of these, the higher melting and therefore the *cis*-isomer was found to have an IR spectrum identical with (–) deoxycarpamic acid. The two alkyl side chains in carpamic acid and therefore in carpaine have a *cis*-relationship to each other. In the chair conformation of the piperidine ring, these would be equatorial. Since carpamic acid was recovered unchanged after prolonged refluxing with sodium pentyloxide, it was considered that the hydroxyl group at C₃ was in the more stable equatorial position, i.e., the groups at C₂ and C₃ had a *trans*-relationship. It was however pointed out by Sicher that the hydroxyl band in the IR spectrum of ethyl carpamate was very similar to that of *cis*-2-methyl-3-hydroxypiperidine with $E_b/E_f=3.6$ and quite unlike that of the *trans*-isomer. The groups in carpaine should therefore have an *all-cis*-relationship.

A second alkaloid named Ψ -carpaine, isomeric with carpaine was isolated at Presidency College⁸. Hydrolysis of this base yielded equal amounts of carpamic and Ψ -carpamic acids. Dehydrogenation of ethyl- Ψ -carpamate yielded ethyl carpyrinate. Thus, Ψ -carpaine should have the same gross structure as carpaine, but differ only in stereochemistry. It was considered that since hydrolysis produced both carpamic as well as Ψ -carpamic acids, this difference could only be at the carbon atom bearing the lactonic oxygen and that for some steric reason, hydrolysis of Ψ -carpaine proceeded both by acyl-oxygen as well as alkyl-oxygen fission. The danger of invoking steric reasons when confronted by difficult experimental results became apparent only much later.

A surprising development took place in 1964, when Spitteler and Spitteler⁹ showed that carpaine had the molecular weight 478 by mass spectrum and hence the molecular formula should be C₂₈H₅₀N₂O₄ and not C₁₄H₂₅NO₂ so far accepted. Carpamodiol, obtained by LAH reduction of carpaine had the molecular weight 243 and dideutero carpamodiol, obtained by LAD reduction of carpaine the molecular weight 245. Carpaine should therefore be formulated as the symmetrical dilactone with two identical piperidine moieties (VII). Molecular models show that the molecule is strainless and the piperidine rings are free to assume the stable chair conformation. Carpaine can therefore be more accurately depicted as in (VIII).

VII

VIII

Subsequently, we found that Ψ -carpaine had also the molecular weight 478¹⁰. The mass spectrum of Ψ -carpaine was identical with that of carpaine, but for a minor

8. T. R. Govindachari and N. S. Narasimham, *ibid.*, 1954, 1847.

9. M. Spitteler-Friedmann and G. Spitteler, *Monatsh.*, 1964, **95**, 1234.

10. T. R. Govindachari, K. Nagarajan and N. Viswanathan, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1965, 1907.

difference in the relative intensities of the peaks at m/e 241 and 242. Ψ -carpaine should also be a dilactone. A study of the the NMR spectra of carpaine and Ψ -carpaine afforded valuable insight into their structure and stereochemistry. Chemical evidence has already been adduced that carpaine has two identical halves. In the 100 Mc NMR spectrum, the two C-Me groups at C_2 are seen as one doublet at δ 1.02 ($J=7$ cps) and the protons at C_2 as a broadened quartet at δ 2.86 ($J=7$ cps), showing a further small coupling of 1-2 cps with the protons at C_3 . The protons at C_3 are seen as an unresolved singlet at δ 4.75 with a width at half height of 5-6 cps. Since the piperidine rings are free to assume the chair conformation, the groups at C_2 and C_6 should be both equatorial. If the lactonic bond were equatorial, the protons at C_3 would be axial. In that case, these would have two axial and one equatorial neighbours and a much broader signal would be expected than the one observed. It is therefore reasonable to assign the equatorial position to the C_3 proton and hence the axial position to the lactonic bond in the preferred conformation of the carpaine molecule.

Pseudocarpaine yields on hydrolysis carpamic and Ψ -carpamic acids. It should therefore be a dilactone, with one piperidine moiety having the same stereochemistry as carpaine, the other piperidine moiety differing in some stereochemical detail. The 100 Mc NMR spectrum of Ψ -carpaine shows the two methyl groups at C_2 and C_2' as two separate doublets at δ 1.02 ($J=7$ cps) and δ 1.07 ($J=7$ cps). The proton at C_2 is seen as a broad quartet at δ 2.86. (The proton at C_6 , is also seen here). The proton at C_2' , is seen as an octet at δ 3.16 ($J_1=7$ cps. $J_2=ca$ 3 cps). The smaller coupling was recognisable in the multiplet due to the C-3' proton at δ 4.83.

The almost identical chemical shifts of the protons at C_3 and C_3' , in Ψ -carpaine suggests identical conformation for both, viz. equatorial. The observable difference in the δ -values of the two methyl groups at C_2 and C_2' , and the large difference in the chemical shifts of the protons on the above carbon atoms indicates that the difference between carpaine and Ψ -carpaine lies in the stereochemistry at C_2' , in one half of the molecule.

Very recently Coke and Rice¹¹ have determined the absolute configuration of carpaine by the following sequence of reactions (Chart IV).

Chart IV

The tetradecanol was shown to have the R configuration. The complete structures for carpaine and Ψ -carpaine can therefore be depicted as (IX) and (X) respectively.

IX

X

I shall now discuss the chemistry of echitamine. This was first isolated by Besanez in 1875 from the bark of *Alstonia scholaris*, but the first reliable characterisations were carried out by Goodson and Henry in 1925¹². Several crystalline derivatives were prepared and the alkaloid isolated as the 'hydrochloride' was assigned the molecular formula $C_{22}H_{29}O_4N_2Cl$. Evidence was furnished for the presence of an indole ring and carbomethoxy group. No further work was done on echitamine for many years, till it was taken up for investigation at Presidency College, Madras, in 1958.

It was found that the alkaloid salt $C_{22}H_{29}O_4N_2Cl$ was a quaternary chloride and not a hydrochloride¹³. Echitamine chloride contained one OMe and one NMe groups. Kuhn-Roth estimation indicated the presence of one C-Me group. The chloride showed UV absorption maxima at 235 and 295 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.93, 3.55) which was unchanged even on addition of strong acid. Hodson and Smith¹⁴ had shown that in dihydroindoles in which N_a and N_b are separated by one, two and three carbon atoms, certain spectral characteristics were evident. Those in which N_a and N_b were separated by one carbon, N_a did not protonate even in strong acid but a hypochromic shift of about 10 $m\mu$ was observed. When two carbon atoms separated N_a and N_b , there was no change on adding acid. When three carbon atoms separated N_a and N_b , there was a remarkable change in the spectrum from that of an indoline to a simple benzene spectrum. Since the spectrum of echitamine chloride did not change on addition of acid, it could be inferred that the two nitrogen atoms were not separated by more than two carbon atoms.

The infra-red absorption spectrum of echitamine chloride showed bands at 3.04 (OH), 3.17 (NH), 5.79 (-COOMe) and 13.2 μ (*o*-di-substituted benzene), but no band near 4.15 μ ($\equiv N^+H$).

The ultra-violet absorption spectrum of the acetyl derivative of echitamine chloride (λ_{max} 235, 295 $m\mu$; $\log \epsilon$ 3.94, 3.50) indicated clearly that N_a -acetylation had not taken place. That only *o*-acetylation had occurred was further supported by the infrared absorption spectrum which showed bands at 2.92 (NH), 5.70 and 8.14 μ (OAc).

12. J. A. Goodson and T. A. Henry, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 1640; J. A. Goodson, *ibid.*, 1932, 2626.

13. T. R. Govindachari and S. Rajappa, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 134.

14. H. F. Hodson and G. F. Smith, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 1877.

Mild alkaline hydrolysis of echitamine chloride gave demethyl-echitamine, which was easily shown to be a betaine. In the infra-red absorption spectrum, the ester band at 5.79μ had disappeared, and instead, the COO^- -band made its appearance at 6.25μ .

Reduction of echitamine chloride in aqueous solution at atmospheric pressure and room temperature in presence of Pd/C gave a tertiary base, m.p. $150-165^\circ$, which undoubtedly contained only three oxygen atoms. Since even carbinolamines were unlikely to undergo hydrogenolysis under the extremely mild conditions of this reduction, at an early stage of our work we suggested the possibility of echitamine chloride being actually $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{27}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2\text{Cl} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$. The correct explanation was first given by Conroy et al. who suggested that the proximate product of reduction was so constituted as to lose a molecule of methanol with formation of a lactone. The reduction product was named echitinolide by these authors and correctly formulated as $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$. We came to the same conclusion independently on the basis of experimental evidence to be discussed later. To avoid confusion, we adopt the names echitinolide and isoechitinolide suggested by Conroy et al.

The ease of formation of the tertiary base echitinolide from echitamine chloride suggests that the latter is an allyl quaternary ammonium salt. Further, since echitinolide contains two OMe groups as shown by Kuhn-Roth estimation, the principal step in the reduction can be formulated as:

The cleavage of this bond seems to be a necessary condition for the second step, viz., the interaction of the carbomethoxy group with a hydroxyl group with expulsion of methanol and formation of a δ -lactone, since echitamine chloride itself is stable to hot hydrochloric acid.

The ultra-violet absorption spectrum of echitinolide shows maxima at 247, 310 μ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.90, 3.54), typical of dihydroindole. Both these maxima undergo a hypsochromic shift of about 10 μ in acid solution. On the basis of the work of Hodson and Smith, it can be inferred that N_a and N_b are separated by a single carbon atom. Echitinolide shows infra-red absorption bands at 2.75 (OH), 2.88 (NH) and 5.80 μ (δ -lactone). Acetylation of echitinolide under vigorous conditions yielded a diacetyl derivative, m.p. $210-214^\circ$, in which N_a has been acetylated as indicated by the infra-red (amide band at 6.0 μ) and ultra-violet spectra (λ_{max} 255 μ ; $\log \epsilon$ 4.07; λ_{infr} 282 μ , $\log \epsilon$ 3.53) and a positive Otto reaction. Hence echitinolide (and echitamine chloride also) should contain a free N_aH group. Mild alkaline hydrolysis of O, N-diacetylechitinolide yielded N-acetylechitinolide, m.p. $160-163^\circ$ (amide band at 6.02 μ ; OH band at 2.71 μ).¹⁵

Independently, Birch et al.¹⁶ reported results of their work on echitamine in broad agreement with those discussed above. They further provided conclusive evidence for the presence of an ethylidene group in echitamine chloride and echitinolide, by the isolation in good yield of acetaldehyde on ozonolysis of these compounds. In addition, they obtained

15. T. R. Govindachari and S. Rajappa, *Tetrahedron*, 1961, 15, 132.

16. A. J. Birch, H. F. Hodson and G. F. Smith, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 244.

α -methylbutyric acid by a modified Kuhn-Roth oxidation of dihydroechitinolide (Base C) proving the presence of the feature (XI)

in echitamine chloride. In our experiments it was found that ozonolysis of echitinolide in 2 per cent acetic acid yielded acetaldehyde, but ozonolysis in chloroform solution yielded a small amount of formaldehyde as the only isolable volatile product. Although the reason for this discrepancy is obscure, the presence of an ethylidene group in echitamine chloride can be taken as settled, since there is no indication in the infra-red or N.M.R. spectra of the presence of a vinyl group.

On warming echitinolide with dilute mineral acid, an isomer isoechitinolide, m.p. 180-182°, was formed whose N-acetyl derivative, m.p. 172-173°, (I.R. band at 6.02 μ : no band in the OH region) was identical with the product obtained by warming N-acetylichitinolide with dilute acid. Isoechitinolide was a tertiary base analysing for the formula $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$ like echitinolide. Isoechitinolide could also be obtained by the following sequence of reactions (Chart I): Demethylechitamine was reduced in presence of Pd/C

Chart I

to yield a non-crystalline amino acid (no band in the carbonyl region below 6.3 μ) which on warming with dilute acid yielded isoechitinolide. The latter therefore cannot contain the carbomethoxy group present in echitamine chloride. Two of its oxygen atoms should be present as part of a lactone system. N-Acetylisoechitinolide has no active hydrogen and isoechitinolide can be recovered unchanged after refluxing with methanolic sodium borohydride. The third oxygen atom should therefore be present as an ether function. In agreement, the infra-red spectrum of isoechitinolide does not show any absorption in the hydroxyl region, and shows a peak at 5.7 μ characteristic of a δ -lactone. Ozonolysis of isoechitinolide did not yield any volatile product unlike echitinolide, and N-acetyl-isoechitinolide

was recovered unchanged after prolonged treatment with osmium tetroxide-sodium metaperiodate. There could be no doubt that the ethylidene group present in echitinolide had disappeared as a result of addition of some sort. These results could be rationalized only if echitinolide were itself a lactone and isoechitinolide arises from it by addition of a hydroxyl group to the ethylidene group under acid catalysis with formation of a cyclic ether. Modified Kuhn-Roth oxidation of isoechitinolide did not yield any propionic acid (paper chromatography). The N.M.R. spectrum of isoechitinolide, however, showed conclusive evidence for the formation of an ethyl group attached to a carbon bearing no hydrogen atoms, a feature not present in the N.M.R. spectrum of echitinolide. (Triplet centred at $\delta=0.62$, $J=7$ cps; quartet centred at $\delta=1.31$, $J=7$ cps).

Earlier we had inferred on the basis of U.V. absorption data that echitinolide contained an N_a-C-N_b system. A characteristic feature of such systems is the cleavage of the $-C-N_b$ bond on reduction with zinc and hydrochloric acid. Echitinolide, however, merely underwent the transformation to isoechitinolide (vide supra) under these conditions, there being no other change.

Echitinolide yielded a methiodide under forced conditions. Treatment of an aqueous solution of this methiodide with 2 N alkali led to the immediate separation of a tertiary base, echitinolidemethine, $C_{22}H_{30}O_4N_2$, m.p. 193° (decomp). The remarkable facility with which this transformation occurred was suggestive of the presence of an eserine-like system in echitinolide. Echitinolidemethine showed U.V. absorption maxima at 245, 307 $m\mu$ in ethanol unchanged by the addition of alkali. In ethanolic hydrochloric acid the maxima were shifted to 240 and 297 $m\mu$, suggesting the reformation of the $-C-N_b$ bond cleaved by alkali. These transformations could be formulated as:

Echitinolidemethine was also stable to oxidation by potassium ferricyanide, suggesting that the indolinol hydroxyl group was tertiary. Although fully aware that N_a -unsubstituted 2-hydroxyindolines might be too unstable to exist, and readily change over to the corresponding indolenines, it was considered likely that in the present instance some structural feature stood in the way of such dehydration.

Reduction of echitinolidemethine with zinc and hydrochloric acid yielded desoxyisoechitinolidemethine, $C_{22}H_{30}O_3N_2$, m.p. $200-203^\circ$. In the formation of this compound not only had the indolinol hydroxyl group been hydrogenolysed as expected, but the addition of a hydroxyl group to the ethylidene function had also taken place. The U.V. absorption spectrum of this compound in ethanol solution showed maxima at 247, and 307 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.97, 3.59) unchanged by the addition of 0.5 N acid, since the possibility of recyclization with formation of the N_a-C-N_b system no longer existed after the removal of the indolinol hydroxyl group. But in 6 N acid, the compound exhibited a benzenoid spectrum.

In an attempt to obtain a clue to the skeletal structure present in echitamine, echitinolide was submitted to selenium dehydrogenation. The product, echitamyrine, $C_{12}H_{10}N_2$ was identified as 1'-methylpyrrolo (2':3'-3:4)-quinoline (XII), by comparison with an authentic sample obtained by silver acetate oxidation of calycanthine. Echita-

XII

myrine could conceivably arise either from an α - or a β -type dihydroindole alkaloid with equal facility and did not therefore prove to be of value in the formulation of structure for echitamine.

At this stage, Chatterjee and coworkers¹⁷ put forward a structure for echitamine chloride. This was clearly untenable, since it has been shown that N_a is unsubstituted. It also incorporates the very unlikely eight-membered carbinolamine system. According to this structure demethylechitamine should spontaneously decarboxylate and this is not the case.

Soon after, Conroy and coworkers¹⁸ from Yale University put forward structures for echitamine chloride and all its transformation products which according to them was consistent with all the experimental results obtained by them and by earlier workers. Two important contributions were made by this group. Firstly, that reduction of echitamine chloride resulted not only in the cleavage of the carbon-nitrogen bond, but also in spontaneous lactonisation. Secondly, they showed that the system $\begin{matrix} >C < \\ & \text{CH}_2\text{OH} \\ & \text{COOCH}_3 \end{matrix}$ was present in the alkaloid. On heating echitamine chloride with potassium t-butoxide the compound alloechitamine, $C_{21}H_{26}N_2O_3$ was produced by removal of the $-\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$

XIII

XIV

XV

XVI

17. A. Chatterjee, S. Ghosal and S. Ghosh Majumdar, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1960, 265.

18. H. Conroy, R. Bernasconi, P. R. Brook, R. Ikan, R. Kurtz and K. W. Robinson, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1960, 1.

group by a retro-aldol reaction. Alloechitamine showed carbonyl absorption at 1689 and 1736 cm^{-1} . The low carbonyl absorption was ascribed to a transannular interaction with the tertiary nitrogen atom. These results along with biogenetic considerations led Conroy et al. to formulate echitamine chloride as (XIII), echitinolide as (XIV), isoechitinolide as (XV) and alloechitamine as (XVI).

The failure of echitamine chloride to protonate even in strong acid was ascribed to steric hindrance in the neighbourhood of N_a . The hypsochromic shift observed on addition of acid to echitinolide was ascribed to a conformational transformation in which N_a originally in axial conformation as in (XVII) changed to an equatorial conformation as in (XVIII).

The arguments advanced by Conroy et al to explain the spectral behaviour of echitamine and its transformation products do not appear convincing. Compounds such as 2,16-dihydroakummicine (XIX), closely similar to the structure postulated for echitamine chloride, show only benzenoid absorption even in .5 N acid solution. Diacetylechitamine chloride yields on Emde reduction, diacetylechitamine, in which the carbomethoxy group is still intact. According to the Conroy proposals, this should be formulated as (XX). Unlike in echitinolide, there is no possibility of conformation transformation in this structure, but still the compound shows the hypsochromic shift of 10 μ of both maxima in acid solution.

The deadlock over the structure of echitamine by determination of its structure by X-ray crystallography by Prof. Monteath Robertson¹⁹ and independently by Prof. S. Ramaseshan²⁰ who also determined the absolute configuration. The structure (XXI) does indeed contain the $\text{N}_a\text{-C-N}_b$ system indicated by the UV spectral data. The absolute configuration at C_{15} was the same as in the majority of indole alkaloids.

The six-membered ring containing the primary alcohol and carbomethoxy groups is a distorted boat, with two cis-fused five-membered rings attached to it. The secondary

19. J. A. Hamilton, T. A. Hamor, J. M. Robertson and G. A. Sim, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 63.

20. H. Manohar and S. Ramaseshan, *Current Science*, 1961, 30, 5.

XXIX

XXX

XXXI

Ring C could be opened up by a berberine-cryptopine type oxidation. This could then react in the indolenine form with oxidative coupling of C₁₆ to C₇. Formation of the N_b-C₂ bond and reduction at C₃ would lead to echitamine. Smith has put forward an alternate scheme involving a geissoschizine like intermediate²¹.

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